

Constitution of the Active Principle of *Embelia Ribes*. Part II.

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In Part I of this series (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1926, 6, 577), embelin, the active principle of *Embelia ribes*, was isolated in a perfectly pure and crystalline form and a number of its important derivatives prepared and analysed. The results proved beyond doubt that embelin, which has the formula $C_{18}H_{28}O_4$, contains two highly reactive hydroxy groups giving most of the reactions of a phenolic nature and two ketonic groups. The hydroxy groups were also shown to undergo interesting keto-enol tautomerism, so that, under suitable conditions, embelin behaved as if it had four ketonic groups.

In the present investigation, embelin has been shown to contain two reactive methylene groups since it condenses with two molecules of aldehydes and two molecules of nitroso-compounds in presence of concentrated sulphuric acid, alcoholic sulphuric acid or hydrogen chloride and glacial acetic acid, yielding crystalline products. The condensation products with aldehydes which are generally orange or yellow in colour crystallise with a molecule of water of crystallisation which is lost on continued heating at 120° with partial decomposition of the molecule and also at 70° in vacuum without decomposition. These compounds which are somewhat analogous to stilbene derivatives, yield dibromides with bromine in chloroform or carbon tetrachloride and regenerate the aldehyde by the action of dilute potassium permanganate. But in the latter case the embelin molecule is destroyed by oxidation. The condensation products with nitroso-compounds which are generally dark in colour, are rather easily attacked by even weak reducing agents, regenerating embelin, together with the formation of an aromatic amine corresponding to the original nitroso-derivative. Thus the condensation product of embelin with *p*-nitrosophenol on reduction by zinc dust and caustic soda yields embelin and *p*-aminophenol. Stronger reducing agents yield dihydro-embelin together with an aromatic amine. In both these types of condensations, it has been possible to isolate a few mono derivatives

in which embelin has condensed with only one molecule of aldehyde or nitroso-compound. The following aldehydes and nitroso-compounds have been condensed with embelin: benzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, anisaldehyde, *p*-toluic aldehyde, vanillin, paraldehyde and butyric aldehyde; nitrosobenzene, *p*-nitrosophenol, nitrosoresorcinol, nitrosodimethylaniline and nitroso- β -naphthol.

Embelin was also found to react with ethyl formate and nitrous acid but the condensation product could not be isolated in pure form.

In this connection it was found that embelin undergoes oxidation by nitric acid with formation of *n*-lauric acid together with smaller quantities of oxalic and malonic acids. The formation of *n*-lauric acid somewhat contradicts the results previously obtained by the present authors (Part I, *loc. cit.*), where *isolauric* acid was isolated. This led the authors to reinvestigate the action of potassium permanganate with a large quantity (50 g.) of the material. A white crystalline substance was obtained (12 g.) which on repeated recrystallisation from methyl alcohol finally melted at 43°, and was found to be identical with *n*-lauric acid (mixed m.p.). From the alcoholic mother-liquors, smaller quantities (4.3 g.) of another acid were isolated, melting at 34-35°, and which apparently seemed to have properties somewhat different from those of *n*-lauric acid. It is just possible that it might be identical with the little known *isolauric* acid or it may be a slightly impure specimen of *n*-lauric acid. On account of the impossibility of securing a genuine specimen of *isolauric* acid, its identity could not be definitely established.

From the foregoing results it is quite evident that embelin contains two reactive methylene groups, which fact also accounts for the interesting keto-enol tautomerism which embelin undergoes.

This together with the interesting fact that embelin is very easily attacked by oxidising agents with formation of mainly *n*-lauric acid together with smaller quantities of oxalic and malonic acids, lead us to assign the following provisional formula to embelin

in which the portion within brackets indicates the lauric acid residue, the CO-groups marked by asterisks are true ketonic groups, and the

remaining CO-groups are those which undergo keto-enol tautomerism. Such a formula clearly explains all the observed properties of embelin. Attempts are being made to corroborate such a formula by synthesis.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Condensation of embelin with aldehydes were carried out either by alcoholic sulphuric acid (method I) or by alcoholic hydrogen chloride (method II). Condensations with nitroso-compounds were done by a mixture of absolute alcohol and glacial acetic acid (1:1 by vol., method III). For the sake of abbreviation an example of each of these methods is given, after which the rest of the results is summarised in tabular forms.

Method I. *Benzylidene-embelin*, $C_{18}H_{26}O_4 : CHC_6H_5, H_2O$.—A mixture of embelin (3 g.) and freshly distilled benzaldehyde (2 g) was heated under reflux for three hours on the water-bath with 50 c.c. of absolute alcohol and 5 c.c. of concentrated sulphuric acid. The reaction mixture was poured into water and boiled for some time in an open dish in order to drive off the excess of benzaldehyde. It was then filtered and the residue crystallised from dilute alcohol in pale yellow needles melting at 112° .

The substance is fairly soluble in most of the organic solvents and also in strong caustic alkalis. Treated with concentrated sulphuric acid it partly dissolves with a reddish colour and partly chars forming a black carbonaceous mass. On treatment with dilute potassium permanganate acidified with dilute sulphuric acid, the odour of benzaldehyde is at once perceptible. By the action of alkaline permanganate, it is completely broken down into benzoic, oxalic, malonic and lauric acids. (Found: C, 71.83; H, 8.2; loss on heating at $70^\circ/40$ mm. for six hours, 4.6. $C_{25}H_{32}O_4, H_2O$ requires C, 72.2; H, 8.2; H_2O , 4.3 per cent.).

Method II. *Dibenzylidene-embelin*, $C_{18}H_{24}O_4 : (CHC_6H_5)_2$.—A mixture of benzaldehyde (10 g.) and embelin (3 g.) dissolved in 100 c.c. absolute alcohol was saturated with dry hydrogen chloride at the ordinary temperature. On allowing the mixture to stand for 24 hours, the colour of the solution became dark red and a little dibenzylidene-embelin crystallised out. The alcohol was then evaporated and the excess of benzaldehyde removed in steam. The dark brown crystalline product thus obtained was digested with 40% sodium hydroxide in order to free it from the traces of mono-benzylidene

derivative, and the residue crystallised from 70% acetic acid in brownish-yellow needles, m.p. 142°.

The substance is much less soluble in the ordinary organic solvents than the foregoing mono-derivative, and unlike the latter substance it is insoluble in caustic alkalis. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a reddish-violet colour. (Found: C, 78.95; H, 7.4. $C_{32}H_{36}O_4$ requires C, 79.3; H, 7.4 per cent.).

Method III. *Bis-phenyliminoembelin*, $C_{18}H_{24}O_4 : (N \cdot C_6H_5)_2$.—A mixture of embelin (3 g.) and nitrosobenzene (2 g.), dissolved in a mixture of alcohol and acetic acid (1:1, 100 c.c.), was heated on the water-bath for one hour. On pouring into water a dark brown mass separated which was filtered off and crystallised from dilute alcohol (animal charcoal) in buff coloured needles, m.p. 195° (decomp.). It is fairly soluble in alcohol and acetic acid, and insoluble in chloroform, benzene, water and caustic alkalis. It does not give any colour reaction with concentrated sulphuric acid. (Found: N, 6.05. $C_{30}H_{34}O_4N_2$ requires N, 5.7 per cent.).

Action of Ethyl Formate on Embelin.—Embelin (5 g.) dissolved in dry toluene (250 c.c.) was treated with ethyl formate (3 g.) and finely divided sodium (0.75 g.). The mixture was kept in a refrigerator for 12 hours and then warmed on the water-bath for 2 hours. The solution gradually assumed a blood-red colour and finally set to a crimson-coloured jelly on cooling. The mixture was then acidified with dilute acetic acid and the toluene distilled off in steam. The viscous residue which on cooling became a soft, dark brown, sticky and exceedingly tenacious mass, could not be crystallised or purified for analysis. It dissolves in caustic alkalis with a blood-red colour and is much more soluble than embelin in the ordinary organic solvents. The general properties are also quite different.

Action of Nitrous Acid on Embelin.—Embelin (3 g.) dissolved in 30 c.c. concentrated sulphuric acid was treated with finely divided sodium nitrite (1 g.). The mixture was cooled in ice while being vigorously stirred, and pieces of ice were gradually added until the precipitation of the isonitroso-compound was complete. The substance, which is a bright yellow crystalline compound dissolving in dilute sodium hydroxide with an orange colour, is only stable at the temperature of ice, since on allowing it to attain ordinary temperature, it spontaneously splits off nitrous acid with regeneration of embelin attended with partial oxidation of the latter. The same thing happens if any attempt is made to crystallise it from organic

solvents. On being rapidly heated it burns with emission of sparks. By warming the substance with alcohol, the odour of acetaldehyde becomes at once perceptible.

Action of dilute Nitric Acid on Embelin.—Embelin (20 g.) was heated with dilute nitric acid (250 c.c., *d* 1.15) on the water-bath for 20 hours. The embelin gradually disappeared and a pale yellow oil was formed, which on cooling solidified to a colourless waxy solid. This was filtered off, washed with water and distilled in steam to free it from traces of volatile fatty acids. It was then repeatedly crystallised from methyl alcohol and finally obtained in the form of lustrous plates melting at 43°, and was found to be identical with *n*-lauric acid (mixed m.p.) (yield, 1.9 g.). The alcoholic mother-liquors on collection, evaporation to a small volume and precipitation by water yielded 1.1 g. of another acid melting at 34-35°, whose identity could not be definitely established. It was practically the same compound as that obtained by the action of potassium permanganate on embelin, and described in a previous communication (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929 6, 586) as *isolauric acid*. It may also be a slightly impure specimen of *n*-lauric acid from which the impurity could not be eliminated by repeated crystallisations.

The nitric acid mother-liquors on neutralisation by sodium carbonate, evaporation to a small volume and treatment with calcium chloride yielded a heavy white precipitate which was found to be mainly calcium oxalate mixed with a little calcium malonate. No other acid could be detected.

Condensation Products of Embelin with Aldehydes and Nitroso-Compounds.

Name. (E = embelin).	Formula.	Method of preparation.	Constituents (E = embelin).	Appearance and m.p.	Crystallised from.	Analysis. (theoretical values in brackets).
Disalicylidene - E	$C_{32}H_{36}O_6, H_2O$	I	Salicylaldehyde (2 mols.) + E	Orange-yellow needles, m.p. 152°	Dil. alcohol	C, 71.4(71.9); H, 6.9(7.1).
Dianisylidene - E	$C_{34}H_{40}O_6, H_2O$	I	Anisaldehyde (2 mols.) + E	Orange-needles, m.p. 167°	„ „	C, 72.3(72.5); H, 7.5(7.4),
Divanillidene - E	$C_{34}H_{40}O_8, H_2O$	I	Vanillin (2 mols.) + E	Orange-red needles, m.p. 230°	70% acetic acid	C, 67.6(67.9); H, 7.8(7.8).
Di- <i>p</i> -methylbenzylidene - E	$C_{34}H_{40}O_4, H_2O$	II	<i>p</i> -Toluic aldehyde (2 mols.) + E	Orangeneedles, m.p. 244°	Dil. alcohol	C, 76.7(76.9); H, 7.8(7.9)
Diacetylidene - E	$C_{22}H_{32}O_4, H_2O$	II	Paraldehyde (1 mol.) + E	Yellow needles, m.p. 123°	Dil. acetone	C, 69.3(69.8); H, 8.5(8.5)
Dibutylidene - E	$C_{26}H_{40}O_4, H_2O$	II	Butyric aldehyde (2 mols.) + E	Brown-yellow needles, m.y. 120°	Dil. alcohol	C, 70.8(71.13); H, 9.7(9.8).
Bis- <i>p</i> -hydroxyphenylimino - E	$C_{30}H_{34}O_6N_2$	III	<i>p</i> -Nitrosophenol (2 mols.) + E	Brown needles, m.p. 207°	Acetic acid	N, 5.2(5.4)
Bis- <i>p</i> -dimethylaminophenyl- imino - E	$C_{34}H_{44}O_4N_4$	III	<i>p</i> -Nitrosodimethyl- aniline (2 mols.) + E	Dark brown leaflets, m.p. above 290°	Alcohol	N, 9.6(9.9)
<i>p</i> -Dimethylaminophenyl- imino - E	$C_{26}H_{36}O_4N_2$	II	<i>p</i> -Nitrosodimethyl- aniline (2 mols.) + E	Brown crystalline powder, m.p. above 290°	Dil. alcohol	N, 6.3(6.1)
Bis-2,4-dihydroxyphenyl- imino - E	$C_{30}H_{34}O_8N_2$	III	Mononitroso- resor- cinol (2 mols.) + E	Brown powder, m.p. 230°	...	N, 5.1(5.08)
Bis-2-hydroxynaphthyl- imino - E	$C_{38}H_{38}O_6N_2$	III	Nitroso- β -naphthol (2 mols.) + E	Brown powder, m.p. above 290°	...	N, 4.09(4.5)

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